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Terms and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CaaS	Certification-as-a-Service
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DL	Deep Learning
DoA	Description of the Action
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EC	European Commission
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call
JPA	Java Persistence API
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KR	Key Result
MARI	Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence
MVC	Model, View, Controller
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OSCAL	Open Security Controls Assessment Language
OSS	Open-Source Software
Protobuf	Protocol Buffers
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RCM	Repository of Controls and Metrics
REST	Representational State Transfer
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity System
TWS	Trustworthiness System
UI	User Interface

Executive Summary

This deliverable, the first version of evidence assessment and certification concepts, provides an initial report on the requirements, design, and integration of the WP3 components within the EMERALD framework. The goal of WP3 is to serve as the central integration point for evidence collection and knowledge extraction tools, contributing to the development of a Certification-as-a-Service (CaaS) framework for continuous certification of harmonized cybersecurity schemes by assessing the provided evidence to make appropriate certificate decisions. In particular, WP3 and its deliverables address the key results CERTGRAPH (KR2) by implementing the evidence store as a graph database, OPTIMA (KR3) by providing the optimal set of metrics for a given control of a security scheme, MULTICERT (KR4) by providing certification decision for multiple schemes and INTEROP (KR7) by providing an interoperability layer for trustworthy systems, assessment results, and catalogue data. These key results are measured using the key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in the DoA [1], which are outlined below.

D3.1 is integral to the EMERALD project, aligning with its overarching objective of enabling multi-scheme auditing of cloud services comprising AI systems. This deliverable informs about the development of WP3 components, including the *Clouditor-Orchestrator*, *Clouditor-Assessment*, *Clouditor-Evidence Store*, *Clouditor-Evaluation*, *Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence* (MARI), *Repository of Controls and Metrics* (RCM), and *Trustworthiness System* (TWS).

At the beginning, the purpose of the deliverable, its context, and the document structure are shown. We then aim to demonstrate a clear understanding of the components being discussed and to illustrate how they are placed in the project. For this purpose, we first provide a short description of each component. Secondly, a high-level WP3 architecture as well as the integration in the EMERALD framework is shown. Finally, the main part of this document delves into each component's requirements, design, integration, planned implementation, and advancements within EMERALD.

Providing certificate decisions by meeting the ambitious objectives set in EMERALD requires various tools to work cohesively together: assessing evidence coming from the WP2 evidence collection tools (KPI 4.1); storing evidence in a graph-based database to enable sophisticated assessment of evidence distributed across various layers of a cloud service (KPI 2.1); the RCM component to store catalogues and metrics in an interoperable way (KPIs 7.1 and 7.2), the MARI component to provide metrics that are suitable for a given (set of) security schemes (KPIs 3.1 and 3.2) and the TWS component to improve the auditor's trust in the evidence (KPIs 7.1 and 7.2). To implement these components in a manner that ensures cohesive operation, they must be carefully designed. The main contributions of this deliverable to the project are therefore to demonstrate the purpose and roles of each WP3 component in the project, the definition of the requirements, and the proposed design to ensure seamless implementation and integration in the whole framework.

The structure of the WP3 deliverables closely resembles the software development life cycle (SDLC) approach: This deliverable describes the initial concepts (requirements and design). The next steps include the actual implementation (D3.3 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Implementation-v1” M12) as well as integration (D3.5 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Integration-v1” M15). This cycle is then repeated with the final versions of concepts (D3.2 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Concepts-v2” M18), implementation (D3.4 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Implementation-v2” M24), and integration (D3.6 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Integration-v2” M27), ensuring continuous improvement and refinement of the components (also considering changes occurring in other work packages).

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

The EMERALD project aims to pave the way towards Certification-as-a-Service (CaaS) for continuous certification of harmonized cybersecurity schemes, such as the EUCS [2]. It addresses the critical need for enhanced transparency, accountability, and trustworthiness in European cloud services. The project focuses on developing robust evidence management components and providing a proof of concept for AI certification schemes.

Within this context, WP3 plays a pivotal role by serving as the central integration point for evidence collection and knowledge extraction tools developed in WP2, while also acting as the interface for auditors and pilots who can interact with it via the UI. The main goal of WP3 is to contribute to the CaaS framework by assessing the provided evidence to make appropriate certification decisions.

This deliverable serves as the initial report on the requirements, design, and integration of the WP3 components within the EMERALD project. The main goal is to lay the foundational framework for understanding and developing the WP3 components. This deliverable is also crucial for providing a clear understanding of the role and interaction of each WP3 component and how they collectively contribute to the project's goals.

In summary, this document aims to provide a thorough understanding of the initial concepts, requirements, and design of the WP3 components, setting the stage for their seamless implementation and integration within the EMERALD framework.

1.2 Document structure

This document is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the WP3 components and their roles within the EMERALD project. The rest of this document is structured as follows:

Section 2 presents an overview of the WP3 Architecture. It offers a concise look at the various components of WP3, their high-level architecture, and their integration within the EMERALD framework. This section aims to give readers a clear understanding of how the different components work together to achieve the project's objectives.

Section 3 contains the main contribution of the document: it delves into each component's requirements, design, integration, planned implementation, and advancements within the EMERALD project.

Finally, Section 4 reports the conclusions.

2 WP3 Architecture Overview

This section offers a foundational overview of the WP3 components within the EMERALD project; setting the context for the detailed analysis of each component's requirements, design, integration, planned implementation, and advancements within EMERALD, which will be covered in Section 3. The objective is to provide an initial understanding of the individual components, their interactions, and their integration within the broader EMERALD framework. Rather than an in-depth exploration, this chapter aims to give a concise and clear snapshot of each component.

Section 2.1 provides an overall overview of each WP3 component, offering short explanations to clarify their roles. Section 2.2 presents a high-level architecture of these components, illustrating how they interact and function together – also with other components within the EMERALD framework.

2.1 Overall overview of the Components

WP3 comprises several key components, each playing a crucial role in the evidence assessment and certification process within the EMERALD project (see Figure 1). Below is a brief overview of each component:

The **Clouditor-Evidence Store** functions as a centralized repository for storing evidence collected during the certification process. It utilizes a graph-based database to organize and manage evidence in an efficient and accessible manner. The evidence is sourced from the collector components developed in WP2, ensuring that all relevant data is systematically stored and readily available for assessment.

The **Clouditor-Assessment** component is responsible for assessing the collected evidence (stored in the Clouditor-Evidence Store) and providing the Clouditor-Orchestrator with assessment results. It calculates the assessment results using the metrics provided by the Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM). Note that assessment results are independent from specific certification schemes. It is the Clouditor-Evaluation component that considers specific certification schemes, see below.

The **Clouditor-Orchestrator** is the central component responsible for orchestrating the certification process. It includes the certification graph, providing a snapshot of the cloud service's state. Among others, it offers an interface for compliance managers to select certification schemes (via the EMERALD UI) and coordinates the assessment tools.

The **Clouditor-Evaluation** component is responsible for combining assessment results relevant to a specific control of a certification scheme to create an evaluation result for this control. It uses these assessment results to determine the compliance state of a control, which is either compliant or non-compliant. Which assessment results must be considered is based on the metrics selected by MARI (an assessment result has a direct relationship to a metric since one assessment result presents one metric calculated at a specific time).

The **Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM)** serves as a smart catalogue of controls and metrics. Controls exist mostly in natural language within various security frameworks and standards like the EUCS. In this project, a *control* refers to a specific countermeasure designed to protect cloud services. We follow the definition of OSCAL where a control “*is a requirement or guideline, which when implemented will reduce an aspect of risk related to an information system and its information*”¹. Note that the naming of a control can also differ from security

¹ <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/resources/concepts/terminology/#control>

standard to security standard, e.g., in the EUCS there are controls and requirements, where a *control* provides a more abstract description and puts multiple requirements together, while a *requirement* gives a concrete definition of a countermeasure. A *metric*, on the other hand, refers to a rule (in fact, a measurable value) used to assess one or more properties of a control. The RCM also incorporates other features such as automatic import/export mechanisms to facilitate the reuse and composition of the catalogue elements.

The **Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence (MARI)** is an intelligent system designed to select suitable metrics for demonstrating compliance with certification schemes. It leverages advanced AI techniques, including Natural Language Processing, to analyse security controls and recommend optimal metrics. MARI also collaborates with the Cluditor-Orchestrator to ensure that the selected metrics align with the certification schemes and facilitate accurate assessments.

The **Trustworthiness System (TWS)** enhances the integrity and transparency of the certification process. It deploys a general-purpose Blockchain network, thereby improving the trustworthiness of the evidence and assessment results. By leveraging blockchain technology, TWS ensures that all actions and data within the certification process are tamper-proof and verifiable, thus boosting the trust of the auditors.

Section 2.2 presents how all these components collectively contribute to achieve WP3 goals.

2.2 Architectural Overview and Integration of WP3 components

Section 3 will present the components of WP3 in detail. We will now consider them within the bigger picture, examining which components communicate with each other and what information they exchange. We also look at the communication to other components within the EMERALD framework. Note that the specific data attributes of the shared information are provided in D1.1 [3].

For the sake of clarity, we will show the typical workflow in EMERALD to demonstrate how the various components work together. Figure 1 shows the current status of all the framework components, as well as their interactions. The goal is to check the compliance of a given cloud service with respect to a certification scheme (e.g., EUCS [2], which is typically divided into several controls (e.g., KCM-02 ENCRYPTION OF DATA IN TRANSIT).

Figure 1. Overview of the EMERALD components [3]

The collector components of WP2 (orange boxes in Figure 1) discover information from the cloud services, e.g., the AI-SEC component collects information about one or more AI systems deployed in the cloud. This information is transformed into a uniform format defined in WP2, known as the ontology for the certification graph (*CertGraphOntology*), which is described in D2.1 [4].

Evidence are then sent to the **Clouditor-Evidence Store**, which stores them in a graph database and forwards them to the Clouditor-Assessment component. The **Clouditor-Assessment** creates assessment results based on the input evidence and one or more rules (i.e., metrics). The assessment component then sends information to the **Clouditor-Orchestrator** (where it is stored in a database), as well as to the **TWS**, which stores hashes of both evidence and assessment results to ensure and prove their integrity (details are explained in Section 3.7).

The Clouditor-Orchestrator sends the assessment results to the **Clouditor-Evaluation**, which decides whether a given cloud service is compliant with respect to a control. Therefore, the Orchestrator needs to know which assessment results are relevant for which controls. Each assessment result is tied to one metric. Typically, multiple metrics (i.e., multiple assessment results at a specific point in time as well) are aggregated to fulfil one control. To support the decision on which metrics are needed, the **MARI** component leverages AI techniques to find the optimal set of metrics for a given control.

All metrics, as well as the various security catalogues, are stored in the **RCM** component. Both the Clouditor-Orchestrator and MARI retrieve the suitable information from there.

Once information on compliance for the individual controls of a security catalogue is available, a decision must be made as to whether the cloud service obtains certification. This decision is ultimately made in the **Clouditor-Orchestrator**, which provides a snapshot of the cloud service's status.

It is possible to communicate with the WP3 components via API interfaces to retrieve, add, or modify information. However, the recommended way for both auditors and cloud services (pilots) is to perform the corresponding operations via the UI (see the blue EMERALD UI box at the top of Figure 1).

This integrated architecture ensures that all components interact effectively to achieve the project's goals. Each component has a specific role, but they are all interconnected, working together to provide a comprehensive and reliable certification process within the EMERALD framework. In Section 3, we will take a closer look how the individual components work.

More detailed information about the architecture will be available in the WP1 “Concept and Methodology of EMERALD” deliverables, particularly in D1.3 “EMERALD solution architecture-v1” (M12) and D1.4 “EMERALD solution architecture-v2” (M24).

3 WP3 Components

This section provides an overview of each component of WP3 of the EMERALD project. It describes the requirements, design, integration, planned implementation, and advancements made for each component.

Each requirement is presented along the common EMERALD requirement definition table consisting of the following fields:

- **Requirement id:** Contains the unique identifier for the requirement.
- **Short title:** Contains a short title for the requirement.
- **Description:** Describes the requirement in more detail.
- **Status:** Contains the status of the requirement, consisting of one of the following values: Proposed → Accepted/Discarded → Work in Progress → Implemented (Partial/Full) → Tested → Validated
- **Priority:** Priority values are: Must; Should; Could.
- **Component:** Contains the name of the component the requirement is related to.
- **Source:** Defines where the requirement comes from: Pilot, Component, DoA or KPI.
- **Type:** Describes the type of the requirement. “Technical” in the case of WP3 requirements.
- **Related KR:** Describes the related key result of the DoA.
- **Related KPI:** Describes the related key performance indicator of the DoA (see below).
- **Validation acceptance criteria:** Describe how to validate the requirement.

Please note that this section only shows the technical requirements for each component. There are also other types of requirements, namely user interface and pilot requirements, which are detailed in deliverables D4.1 [5] and D5.1 [6], respectively. To bridge the gap between technical and non-technical requirements, they are currently being linked to each other, so that in the end each need from the user interface and pilot perspective is satisfied in the components.

Finally, WP3 requirements are related to the following **KPIs** [7]:

- **KPI 1.1:** Provide support for evidence extraction from different sources (infrastructure, code, processes).
- **KPI 2.1:** Provide a schema for storing and linking heterogeneous evidence information.
- **KPI 2.3:** Provide scalability for storing/processing continuously collected evidence; demonstrated in the pilots.
- **KPI 3.1:** Provide scheme to scheme mapping functionality based on metrics, recommended to the user.
- **KPI 3.2:** Provide metric-to-requirement-mapping functionality by improving MEDINA approaches and incorporating KPI 5.1 results.
- **KPI 3.3:** Provide insights for the mapping decision and how the recommendation process works.
- **KPI4.1:** Provide realizable metrics that demonstrate compliance to at least two security certification schemes.
- **KPI 4.2:** Provide metric assessment for 80 % of the metrics in KPI 4.1 based on the certification graph.
- **KPI 6.2:** Provide concept for the (UI) of EMERALD and integration of evidence collection components, data bases and orchestrating components.
- **KPI 6.3:** Provide a graphical user interface for role-based access to certification information content.

- **KPI 7.1:** Conventionalize import and export functionalities to take or share data with external sources.
- **KPI 7.2:** Incorporate input from standardisation bodies and synchronize data formats and protocols.

3.1 Cluditor-Orchestrator

The *Cluditor-Orchestrator* is the central component orchestrating the certification process and connecting multiple components together of the EMERALD framework. Finally, this component takes care of the certification decision, i.e., whether a cloud service is compliant with a security catalogue or not. The *Cluditor-Orchestrator* component is based on the respective microservice of *Cluditor*² and was already used in MEDINA [8]. It will be further developed by leveraging the functionality of the *Life-Cycle Manager* component in MEDINA to provide the final certificate decision.

3.1.1 Requirements

The main technical requirements for the *Cluditor-Orchestrator* are as follows:

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ORCH.01
Short title	Final certificate decision
Description	Since we do not have a dedicated life-cycle manager component in EMERALD, the Orchestrator must take care of the final certificate decision. The decision is based on the input of the Evaluation component providing the Orchestrator with an evaluation result for each control.
Status	Accepted
Priority	Must
Component	Cluditor-Orchestrator
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR4_MULTICERT
Related KPI	KPI 4.1, KPI 4.2
Validation acceptance criteria	If an assessment and evaluation fails, the certificate must go to a suspended state.
Progress	0%
Milestone	MS5: Components V2 (M24)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ORCH.02
Short title	REST API Gateway for UI
Description	The Orchestrator should provide a REST API gateway for the UI that serves a central API endpoint for all information needed from the Orchestrator, Assessment, Evaluation and other Cluditor components. This includes:

² <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/orchestrator>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of all controls, catalogues, etc. (which are each cached from the RCM) • List of all cloud services (+add/edit/remove) • List of all "target of evaluations", maybe to be named "audit instances" (+add/edit/remove) • List of all tools (extractors, assessment (+register/edit/remove/disable). See [ORCH.04]) • List of all assessment results • List of all evaluation results • List of all certificates (decisions). See [ORCH.01] • List of all audit workflow assignments (+add/edit/delete comment). See [ORCH.05]
Status	Accepted
Priority	Must
Component	Cloudfitor-Orchestrator
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR6_EMERALD UI/UX
Related KPI	KPI 6.2
Validation acceptance criteria	The Orchestrator has a functioning API endpoint that provides all the required information from the connected Cloudfitor components.
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ORCH.03
Short title	Role Based Access Control
Description	Since the UI wants to selectively disclose information to users and/or roles, we need a RBAC mechanism in our API endpoints, mainly in the Orchestrator.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	Cloudfitor-Orchestrator
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR6_EMERALD UI/UX
Related KPI	KPI 6.3
Validation acceptance criteria	The UI only displays information after a successful login.
Progress	25%
Milestone	MS5: Components V2 (M24)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ORCH.04
Short title	Manage Tools (such as Evidence Extractors) via API

Description	<p>We need to manage external tools, such as evidence extractors in the Orchestrator. We want to have the following functionality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register a new tool (e.g., with a token) for a particular cloud service • "Hello" from the tool -> returns the configured cloud service ID • List all tools • Get status of tool (whatever the status is). Last evidence sent, etc. • Remove tool -> do not accept forever • Disable or suspend tool -> temporarily do not accept evidence, assessment result, etc. from the tool <p>We need different "types" / categories of tools. This needs to be specified (e.g., either evidence extractor or assessment tool) Note: The list of configured tools is specific for a particular cloud service.</p>
Status	Accepted
Priority	Must
Component	Cloudfitor-Orchestrator
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR6_EMERALD UI/UX
Related KPI	KPI 6.3
Validation acceptance criteria	The UI only displays information about registered tools.
Progress	0%
Milestone	MS3: Integrated audit suite V1 (M18)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ORCH.05
Short title	Provide an API for audit workflow
Description	<p>We want to assign people to controls within an audit instance that have a particular task. The exact definition of this has to be done. Probably we want to have the possibility to add comments to controls? Maybe also add the manual evidence? Status of the control?</p>
Status	Accepted
Priority	Must
Component	Cloudfitor-Orchestrator
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR6_EMERALD UI/UX
Related KPI	KPI 6.3
Validation acceptance criteria	All the controls of the scheme are displayed with the required information.
Progress	0%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

3.1.2 Design

The *Clouditor-Orchestrator* is based on the respective microservice of *Clouditor*³, whose modular architectural approach ensures scalability and flexibility. Key design elements of the *Clouditor-Orchestrator* in EMERALD include:

- **Workflow Management:** The *Orchestrator* manages the workflow of the certification process, coordinating with other components to ensure that evidence is collected, assessed, and evaluated in a timely and efficient manner. It ensures that each step in the certification process is executed correctly, from the initial collection of evidence to the final certification decision. This involves scheduling tasks, handling dependencies between different components, and ensuring that all necessary actions are completed to achieve compliance with the selected certification schemes.
- **Modular Architecture:** The *Orchestrator* component is part of the *Clouditor* tool, which is built using a microservice architecture. This architecture divides the *Clouditor* tool into multiple independent services that can be developed, deployed, and scaled separately. The *Orchestrator* is one of these microservices, responsible for orchestrating the certification process. Other microservices within *Clouditor* include the *Discovery* and *Assessment* services, among others. This modularity allows for easier maintenance and scalability, as each microservice can be updated or scaled independently.
- **Communication protocols (API endpoints):** A RESTful API is provided to facilitate interactions with the UI and other components. Additionally, the *Orchestrator*, as well as other *Clouditor* components (e.g., *Discovery* and *Assessment*), are able to communicate via gRPC. This dual API approach ensures flexibility in the communication protocols, allowing for efficient data exchange and integration with various systems. The APIs serve as central endpoints for retrieving and managing information from the *Orchestrator*, *Assessment*, *Evaluation*, and other *Clouditor* components.
- **User Interface:** The *Orchestrator* integrates with the EMERALD UI, allowing compliance managers to interact with the system. The UI provides functionalities for selecting certification schemes, viewing assessment results, and making final certification decisions.
- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** To ensure that information is selectively disclosed to users based on their roles, the *Orchestrator* implements an RBAC mechanism. This mechanism controls access to API endpoints and ensures that only authorized users can view or modify specific information.

3.1.3 Integration

Because it plays the central role (see Section 2.2) in orchestrating many components and their data flows, the integration of the *Clouditor-Orchestrator* with other components within the EMERALD framework is crucial for achieving a seamless certification process. The following components the *Clouditor-Orchestrator* is communicating with:

- **EmeraldUI:** The *Orchestrator* integrates with the EMERALD UI, allowing compliance managers and other users to interact with the system. The UI provides functionalities for selecting certification schemes, viewing assessment results and final certification decisions. The UI communicates with the *Orchestrator* through the REST API.
- **Clouditor-Assessment:** The *Orchestrator* receives assessment results sent by the *Assessment* component which is then used to create evaluation results. The *Clouditor-Assessment* communicates with the *Orchestrator* via gRPC allowing sending of assessment results with high performance.

³ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/orchestrator>

- **Clouditor-Evaluation:** The *Orchestrator* utilizes the *Evaluation* component to send the respective assessment results to get evaluation results for given controls. These results are the base for making the certification decision and ensuring compliance with the selected certification schemes.
- **Clouditor-Evidence Store:** The *Orchestrator* supplies the *Evidence Store* with meta data, e.g., the ID of the respective cloud service.
- **Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM):** The *Orchestrator* accesses the RCM to retrieve relevant metrics and controls (as well as the respective mapping provided by MARI). This information is used to define assessment criteria and ensure that the certification process aligns with the required standards. The RCM communicates with the *Orchestrator* through the REST API.

3.1.4 Planned Implementation

The planned implementation of the *Clouditor-Orchestrator* involves several functionalities and utilizes a specific technology stack to ensure efficient and effective operation. Below is an overview of the planned functionalities and the technology stack.

Functionalities:

- Orchestration Module, i.e., orchestrating components and controlling the data flow
- API Gateway, i.e., providing REST API allowing other components communicating with the Orchestrator that only support RESTful APIs
- Compliance checking, i.e., calculate evaluation and certification decision
- Support RBAC, allowing only authorized users to access or modify specific information

Technology Stack:

- Go as programming language, providing simple and efficient implementation, concurrency support, and ease of deployment in microservice architectures
- Communication Protocols: REST API and gRPC (including Protobuf)

3.1.5 Advancements within EMERALD

One goal within the EMERALD project is to adopt the *Clouditor* tool by increasing its Technology Readiness Level (TRL) from 5 to 7. Most of the enhancements will be made in other components of the *Clouditor* tool, e.g., by providing graph-based evidence in the *Clouditor-Evidence Store*. However, in addition to improving code quality, performance, and fixing bugs, *Clouditor-Orchestrator* will also include the functionality to make final certification decisions. Previously, in the MEDINA project, the certification decision was handled by a different tool (see section 4.4.2 of D5.5 [8]).

3.2 Cloditor-Assessment

The *Cloditor-Assessment* component is responsible for assessing evidence based on predefined metrics. The calculated assessment results are inspired by, but de-coupled from the actual controls of security catalogues. These results are eventually used by the *Cloditor-Evaluation* component to determine compliance with the relevant controls. The *Cloditor-Assessment* component is based on the respective microservice of *Cloditor*⁴ and was already used in MEDINA [8]. It will be further developed to handle multiple pieces of evidence that reflect resources on different layers.

3.2.1 Requirements

The main technical requirements for the *Cloditor-Assessment* component are as follows:

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ASSESS.01
Short title	Assessment based on evidence
Description	The assessment should assess evidence based on the knowledge graph.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	Cloditor-Assessment
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR4_MULTICERT
Related KPI	KPI 4.1, KPI 4.2
Validation acceptance criteria	Evidence can be retrieved and assessed by the assessment component.
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ASSESS.02
Short title	Assessment rules for 80% of the defined metrics
Description	Assessment rules must exist for 80% of the metrics defined in KP4.1.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	Cloditor-Assessment
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR4_MULTICERT
Related KPI	KPI 4.2
Validation acceptance criteria	Existence of assessment rules for 80% of the defined metrics. Existence of unit tests for all assessment rules.
Progress	15%

⁴ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/assessment>

Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)
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Field	Description
Requirement ID	ASSESS.03
Short title	Display cause of assessment result
Description	We want to know why an assessment result fails or passes.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Could
Component	Clouditor-Assessment
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR6_EMERALD UI/UX
Related KPI	KPI 6.3
Validation acceptance criteria	The cause why an assessment results fails or passes is shown in the EmeraldUI.
Progress	0%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

3.2.2 Design

The *Clouditor-Assessment* is based on the respective microservice of *Clouditor*⁵, whose modular architecture approach ensures scalability and flexibility. Key design elements of the *Clouditor-Assessment* in EMERALD include:

- **Modular Architecture:** The *Clouditor-Assessment* component is one of *Clouditor* microservices, responsible for evaluating evidence based on predefined metrics. This modularity allows for easier maintenance and scalability, as each microservice can be updated or scaled independently.
- **Assessment Engine:** The core of the *Clouditor-Assessment* component is the assessment engine, which processes the collected evidence based on predefined metrics. The engine calculates the evidence and generates assessment results, identifying compliance and non-compliance areas. Because the evidence follows the scheme of the graph ontology, it has a unified format. This unified format allows the definition of metrics to assess evidence independent of the extraction component and actual source the evidence is coming from. For example, if the incoming evidence is of type "*VirtualMachine*", the ontology presets how the evidence extractor has to form the evidence. Among others, it has to set if boot logging is enabled (it does not matter if it was collected by *Clouditor-Discovery* or by some other tool. Also, it doesn't matter which actual cloud service the information is collected from). Therefore, we can create a simple metric that checks if boot logging is enabled for such incoming evidence, thus decoupling assessment and evidence extraction. For now, we use the policy language Rego with its respective Go Client to write and apply metrics, respectively⁶. We plan to keep using Rego, but it is open whether we need to find another solution due to the new graph database concept.
- **Assessment Reporting:** The *Clouditor-Assessment* component generates comments that include the causes of any failing assessment results. These comments are essential

⁵ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/assessment>

⁶ <https://www.openpolicyagent.org/docs/latest/policy-language/>

for understanding why a particular assessment status is non-compliant giving an auditor more information about certain evidence.

- **Communication Protocols (API endpoints):** The *Clouditor-Assessment* component communicates with other *Clouditor* components, such as the *Orchestrator*, via gRPC. This ensures high-performance interactions and efficient data exchange. Additionally, the component provides a REST endpoint for communication with other components not supporting gRPC.
- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** To ensure that information is selectively disclosed to users based on their roles, the *Clouditor-Assessment* component implements an RBAC mechanism. This mechanism controls access to API endpoints and ensures that only authorized users can view or modify specific information.

3.2.3 Integration

The following components communicate with the *Clouditor-Assessment*, as shown in Figure 1:

- **Clouditor-Orchestrator:** The *Assessment* component coordinates with the *Orchestrator* to receive instructions and send back assessment results. In addition, the metrics are initially imported from the *Orchestrator* (originating from the RCM). Communication between the *Assessment* component and the *Orchestrator* is facilitated via gRPC.
- **Clouditor-Evidence Store:** The *Assessment* component retrieves evidence from the *Clouditor-Evidence Store* to perform assessments. The communication with the *Evidence Store* is also done via gRPC to ensure high-performance data exchange.
- **Trustworthiness System (TWS):** The *Assessment* component interacts with the TWS to provide assessment results as well as the respective evidence. The *Assessment* component communicates with the TWS to enhance the integrity and trust of the assessment process for auditors and other users. The *Assessment* component communicates with the TWS through a REST endpoint.

This integration ensures that the *Clouditor-Assessment* component can efficiently gather and process evidence, collaborate with other components, and provide accurate assessment results to support the overall certification process in the EMERALD framework.

3.2.4 Planned Implementation

The planned implementation of the *Clouditor-Assessment* component involves one main functionality and utilizes a specific technology stack to ensure efficient and effective operation. Below is an overview of the planned functionalities and the technology stack.

Functionalities:

- The main functionality is to process evidence from various sources and assess it based on predefined metrics. This includes handling multiple pieces of evidence that reflect resources on different layers, ensuring a comprehensive assessment process. The processing of this multi-layered evidence is achieved by representing evidence in a graph-based way.

Technology Stack:

- **Programming Language:** As all *Clouditor* components, the *Clouditor-Assessment* component is implemented in Go, providing a simple and efficient implementation, concurrency support, and ease of deployment in microservice architectures.
- **Communication Protocols:** The component uses gRPC (including Protobuf) for communication with other *Clouditor* components, enabling the handling of thousands

of pieces of evidence per minute, which is essential for managing the high volume of resources in distributed environments such as in a cloud. It also provides a REST endpoint for interaction with the TWS, ensuring flexible and efficient communication across the system.

3.2.5 Advancements within EMERALD

Unlike the *Orchestrator*, the improvements in the *Clouditor-Assessment* component with respect to the MEDINA version are substantial, as it will support the assessment of evidence distributed across various layers of a cloud service. This enhancement will allow for a more comprehensive and accurate assessment, accommodating the complexity of modern cloud environments. Additionally, improvements in code quality, performance, and bug fixes will further enhance the reliability and efficiency of the *Assessment* component.

3.3 Clouditor-Evidence Store

The *Clouditor-Evidence Store* component is responsible for storing and managing evidence of different resource types and collected from various sources. The primary challenge it addresses is transitioning to a storage system representing a graph database, as we are moving towards a certification graph (KR2 CERTGRAPH), so the component is an implementation of the schema developed and defined in WP2, as described in D2.1 [9]. The *Evidence Store* is designed to allow complex assessments and is based on the respective microservice of *Clouditor*⁷, which was already used in MEDINA [8], but now it is planned to support graph-based evidence.

3.3.1 Requirements

The main technical requirements for the *Clouditor-Evidence Store* component are as follows:

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ESTORE.01
Short title	Storage of evidence as ontology entities in graph database
Description	The Evidence Store must store the evidence according to the schema defined by the knowledge graph. The preferred way to store this information is a graph database.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	Clouditor-EvidenceStore, Clouditor-Assessment
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR2_CERTGRAPH
Related KPI	KPI 2.1, KPI 2.3
Validation acceptance criteria	Evidence entity can be successfully retrieved by the assessment component.
Progress	15% (examination of DB candidates)
Milestone	MS3: Integrated audit suite V1 (M18)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	ESTORE.02
Short title	Allow Interaction with Third-Party Tools

⁷ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/evidence>

Description	The Evidence store should be allowed to accept evidence from third-party tools, e.g., using a REST API. The evidence needs to be in the ontology format. Therefore, information about the ontology and data models must be available.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Should
Component	Clouditor-EvidenceStore
Source	KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR1_EXTRACT
Related KPI	KPI 1.1
Validation acceptance criteria	The Evidence Store stores evidence from third-party evidence collectors.
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS8: Integrated audit suite V3 (M34)

3.3.2 Design

The *Clouditor-Evidence Store* is based on the respective microservice of *Clouditor*⁸ whose modular architectural approach ensures scalability and flexibility. Key design elements of the *Clouditor-Evidence Store* in EMERALD include:

- **Modular Architecture:** The *Evidence Store* is one of *Clouditor* microservices, responsible for efficiently storing and managing evidence. This modularity allows for easier maintenance and scalability, as each microservice can be updated or scaled independently.
- **Graph Database:** The *Evidence Store* will utilize a graph-based database to store all the evidence as a certification graph. This database structure allows for efficient organization, retrieval, and updating of evidence, making it well-suited for managing complex relationships between different types of evidence at possibly different layers (e.g., infrastructure vs code).
- **Communication Protocols (API endpoints):** The *Evidence Store* will use gRPC (including Protobuf) for the communication with other *Clouditor* components, ensuring high-performance interaction. Additionally, it will provide REST endpoints for flexible and efficient communication with evidence collectors not supporting gRPC.
- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** To ensure that information is selectively disclosed to users based on their roles, the *Evidence Store* implements an RBAC mechanism. This mechanism controls access to API endpoints and ensures that only authorized users can view or modify specific information.

3.3.3 Integration

The integration of the *Clouditor-Evidence Store* component with other components in the EMERALD framework is essential for efficient evidence management and retrieval. The following components communicate with the *Clouditor-Evidence Store*, as shown in Figure 1:

- **Evidence Collectors:** The *Evidence Store* is designed to interact with various evidence collectors, which gather evidence from different sources. While gRPC is the primary protocol for high-performance communication, the *Evidence Store* also provides REST endpoints to accommodate evidence collectors that do not support gRPC.

⁸ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/evidence>

- **Clouditor-Assessment:** The *Evidence Store* supplies the *Assessment* component with the required evidence for its assessment calculation. This interaction is also managed via gRPC, enabling the *Assessment* component to send evidence quickly and efficiently.
- **Clouditor-Orchestrator:** The *Evidence Store* retrieves meta data from the *Orchestrator*, e.g., the ID of the respective cloud service to add this information to the incoming evidence.

3.3.4 Planned Implementation

The planned implementation of the *Clouditor-Evidence Store* component involves utilizing a graph-based database to effectively store and manage evidence. Below is an overview of the planned functionality and the technology stack.

Functionalities:

The *Clouditor-Evidence Store* will utilize a graph-based database to store the certification graph. This database structure allows for efficient organization, retrieval, and updating of evidence, making it well-suited for managing complex relationships between different types of evidence at various levels. We have been examining over 30 graph database candidates⁹ and are now in the phase of testing to find the most suitable one. The strict criteria for these databases are that they must be open source with a suitable licence, i.e., compatible with Apache 2.0¹⁰ and compatible with Go, e.g., by providing a Go client.

Technology Stack:

The component is implemented in Go, providing simple and efficient implementation, concurrency support, and ease of deployment in microservice architectures. Communication protocols include gRPC (including Protobuf) for high-performance interaction with other Clouditor components and REST endpoints for flexible communication with evidence collectors not supporting gRPC. Additionally, the *Clouditor-Evidence Store* will implement Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) to ensure that information is selectively disclosed to users based on their access rights.

3.3.5 Advancements within EMERALD

The *Clouditor-Evidence Store* will support storing and managing evidence in a graph-based database, namely as a certification graph. This enhancement allows for efficient organization, retrieval, and updating of evidence, accommodating the complexity of modern cloud environments. Additionally, improvements in code quality, performance, and bug fixes will further enhance the reliability and efficiency of the *Evidence Store* component.

3.4 Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence (MARI)

MARI is an intelligent system capable of selecting the optimal set of metrics to associate with one or more certification schemes. These metrics can be measured to evaluate the cloud system's compliance within the certification schemes. The MARI component is based on the *Metric Recommender*¹¹ tool developed in MEDINA [8].

⁹ <https://db-engines.com/en/ranking/graph+dbms>

¹⁰ <https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html>

¹¹ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/nl2cml-translator>

The objective of MARI is to experiment with Deep Learning and state-of-the-art NLP tools to create automatic associations between:

- a security control and one or more security metrics
- two security controls coming from two different certification schemes.

3.4.1 Requirements

Field	Description
Requirement ID	MARI.01
Short title	AI-based
Description	MARI is a tool based on state-of-the-art artificial intelligence, e.g., uses a transformer-based architecture
Status	Approved
Priority	Must
Component	MARI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR3_OPTIMA
Related KPI	KPI 3.1, KPI 3.2, KPI 3.3
Validation acceptance criteria	MARI uses state-of-the-art tools, such as transformer-based architectures, to produce the control-metric(s) association
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	MARI.02
Short title	Automatic association
Description	MARI takes as input cloud security controls written in natural language, metrics that validate those controls, again written in natural language, and automatically returns as output the association control/metric(s) and the association control/control.
Status	Approved
Priority	Must
Component	MARI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR3_OPTIMA
Related KPI	KPI 3.1, KPI 3.2, KPI 3.3
Validation acceptance criteria	The output consists of a list of control/metric(s) pairs. The output consists of a list of control/control pairs (and the controls comes from diverse certification schemes).
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	MARI.03

Short title	Performance Evaluation
Description	The performance of MARI should improve on the performance of the <i>Metric Recommender</i> of EMERALD's predecessor project, MEDINA. We can assume that we measure the performance of MARI with the same metrics used for the <i>Metric Recommender</i> , namely precision@k and NDCG (Normalised Discounted Cumulative Gain) ¹²
Status	Approved
Priority	Must
Component	MARI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR3_OPTIMA
Related KPI	KPI 3.1, KPI 3.2, KPI 3.3
Validation acceptance criteria	Better performances than the <i>Metric Recommender</i> predecessor
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	MARI.04
Short title	Usage and Visualization
Description	MARI should be invoked through EMERALD's built-in interface, and MARI results can be visualized through the same interface
Status	Approved
Priority	Must
Component	MARI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR3_OPTIMA
Related KPI	KPI 3.1, KPI 3.2, KPI 3.3
Validation acceptance criteria	It is possible to call MARI via the EMERALD's built-in interface and the results are visualized in the same interface
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	MARI.05
Short title	Strategies
Description	MARI can act according to specific strategies, such as considering only technical controls, or organizational controls, or controls of a certain category, or controls whose implementation costs less in terms of human resources, etc. The strategies will be defined during the project.

¹²<https://towardsdatascience.com/evaluation-metrics-for-recommendation-systems-an-overview-71290690ecba>

Status	Approved
Priority	Must
Component	MARI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR3_OPTIMA
Related KPI	KPI:3.1, KPI: 3.2, KPI:3.3
Validation acceptance criteria	It is possible to obtain the control/metric(s) association selecting at least two strategies defined during the project
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

3.4.2 Design

The implementation of MARI starts from the MEDINA tool named *Metric Recommender*¹³ [8], which takes the description of an EUCS security requirement in natural language, the description of a list of metrics, again in natural language, and as a result returns the list of metrics in descending order of relevance. MARI's implementation will take inspiration from the *Metric Recommender* and will introduce some novelties, as introduced below.

In particular, there are two tasks that MARI performs. The first is to associate a security control with one or more metrics. The second is to associate a control of a certification scheme with a similar control of another certification scheme.

By enabling the mapping of security controls from different certification schemes, MARI will allow reuse of metrics associated with control X of certification scheme A for controls associated with X but belonging to other certification schemes. Thus, the same metric can be mapped to controls across different schemes. Consequently, this will reduce the time and cost required to assess compliance with a given certification scheme. Ultimately, the system aims to assist and streamline the compliance manager's tasks.

The intelligent system will employ cutting-edge Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) for encoding controls and metrics originally stated in natural language, and Deep Learning (DL) (specifically, transformer-based models) for the association between controls and metrics, and between controls and controls. Additionally, various optimization strategies will be explored to choose the most effective subset of metrics to be measured or meet specific criteria set by the compliance manager.

3.4.3 Integration

The following components communicate with MARI as shown in Figure 1:

- **Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM):** MARI will interact with the RCM because MARI inputs (i.e., controls and metrics) are stored therein. It will also return the control/control associations and the control/metric associations to the RCM.
- **EmeraldUI:** MARI will also interface with the EMERALD UI developed in WP4, through which it will be possible to view the results of control/metric associations and control/control associations.

¹³ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/nl2cnl-translator>

3.4.4 Planned Implementation

The MEDINA *Metric Recommender* was implemented in Python using different Python libraries to apply the various steps needed for the approach. In particular, the textual descriptions of the metrics and controls were transformed into feature vectors by pre-trained models (fastText¹⁴). A K-d tree was then computed on the feature vectors of the metrics, which were used to select the k closest neighbours of the control vector, based on the shortest Euclidean distance.

For the implementation of MARI, we plan to stick to Python as programming language, but we plan to adopt new libraries for computing the associations. As for the APIs, we will adapt the existing ones in MEDINA [8] (See Appendix -> 13.2 Component: NL2CNL Translator). More details will be described in the upcoming WP3 deliverables.

3.4.5 Advancements within EMERALD

Compared to its predecessor, the MEDINA *Metric Recommender*, MARI will work with more controls from more certification schemes.

Of note, MARI will allow controls belonging to different certification schemes to be automatically mapped, something that had to be done manually in the predecessor project, MEDINA. The user will be able to specify strategies to follow in the control/metric (s) association process as well as in the control/control association.

At the level of AI-based tools, the use of transformer-based architectures is expected. Furthermore, it is planned to improve performance with respect to the *Metric Recommender* and to improve the accuracy of association between metrics and controls.

3.5 Cluditor-Evaluation

The *Cluditor-Evaluation* component is responsible for evaluating the compliance of cloud services against controls of security catalogues. This component addresses the challenge of aggregating and interpreting assessment results to determine overall compliance status for a given control. It is based on the respective microservice in *Cluditor*¹⁵.

3.5.1 Requirements

The main requirements for the *Cluditor-Evaluation* component are as follows:

Field	Description
Requirement ID	EVAL.01
Short title	Display cause of failing evaluation result
Description	We want to know why the evaluation result fails or passes. Therefore, it should contain a list of assessment results that cause the evaluation status to be <i>non-compliant</i> .
Status	Accepted
Priority	Could
Component	Cluditor-Evaluation
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR6_EMERALD UI/UX
Related KPI	N.A.

¹⁴ <https://fasttext.cc/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/evaluation>

Validation acceptance criteria	The cause why an evaluation result fails or passes is shown in the evaluation results.
Progress	0%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	EVAL.02
Short title	Evaluation based on assessment results
Description	The evaluation should assess the result based on all the required assessment results stored in the database.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	Clouditor-Evaluation
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR4_MULTICERT
Related KPI	N.A.
Validation acceptance criteria	Assessment results can be retrieved via the <i>Orchestrator</i> and evaluated by the <i>Evaluation</i> component.
Progress	15%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

3.5.2 Design

The design of the *Clouditor-Evaluation* component focuses on modularity, scalability, and flexibility to effectively evaluate compliance based on assessment results. Key design elements include:

- **Modular Architecture:** The *Evaluation* component is one of *Clouditor* microservices¹⁶, responsible for evaluating compliance based on assessment results. This modularity allows for easier maintenance and scalability, as each microservice can be updated or scaled independently.
- **Compliance Evaluation:** The core functionality of the *Evaluation* component is to assess compliance by analysing assessment results. It evaluates the results against controls of security catalogues, determining whether one or more metrics meet the required standards for certification.
- **Communication Protocols:** The *Evaluation* component uses gRPC for high-performance communication with the *Orchestrator*.
- **Evaluation Reporting:** The *Evaluation* component generates comments or reports that include the causes of any failing evaluation results. These are essential for understanding why a particular evaluation status is non-compliant and for making informed decisions.
- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC):** To ensure that evaluation information is selectively disclosed to users or clients based on their roles (communication with the *Orchestrator*), the *Evaluation* component implements an RBAC mechanism.

¹⁶ <https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor/tree/main/service/evaluation>

3.5.3 Integration

The *Cloudditor-Evaluation* component primarily communicates with the *Cloudditor-Orchestrator* (see Figure 1). The *Orchestrator* coordinates the flow of assessment results to the *Evaluation* component, enabling it to perform compliance evaluations based on these results. This interaction is facilitated via gRPC, ensuring efficient and high-performance communication.

3.5.4 Planned Implementation

Below is an overview of the planned functionalities and the technology stack:

- The *Evaluation* component will be responsible for processing assessment results obtained from the *Cloudditor-Orchestrator* and determining the compliance status based on predefined criteria (mapping of metrics to controls of a security catalogue). The criteria is given by the selection of MARI (see Section 3.4.2). This process involves analysing the assessment results (of the respective metrics), identifying non-compliance areas, and generating an evaluation report.
- The *Evaluation* component will be implemented by using the programming language Go, providing a simple and efficient implementation with strong concurrency support. Communication between the *Evaluation* component and the *Cloudditor-Orchestrator* will be facilitated via gRPC, allowing the transmission of thousands of assessment results per minute.

3.5.5 Advancements within EMERALD

As the *Evaluation* component is a rather small and internal service, there will be no major developments with respect to the current service apart from adaptations of the code to the EMERALD framework and bug fixes. The only significant enhancement foreseen is the examination of different aggregation strategies for evaluating the assessment results of a given control.

3.6 Repository of controls and metrics (RCM)

The *Repository of Controls and Metrics* (RCM) provides a central point in the EMERALD framework where the **certification schemes are stored and managed**. It consists of a repository capable of containing different certification schemes, including the information of each scheme categorized by classes (e.g., categories, controls, requirements, assurance levels, etc.) and supporting multi-scheme and multi-level certification. The RCM also incorporates the definition of the **metrics** used in EMERALD to assess evidence. The RCM implementation is based in the MEDINA component *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics*¹⁷ [8].

The RCM will provide mechanisms to update the catalogues and maintain a versioning system, and will foster the interoperability using OSCAL¹⁸ as exchange format. This feature will allow importing and exporting catalogues into/from the RCM. In addition, the RCM will manage other information, such as the mappings provided by the MARI component, the guidelines (e.g., guidelines for EUCS requirements are already included) and a self-assessment questionnaire to assess compliance with a scheme.

The RCM provides this information to the rest of the EMERALD components via APIs, which can also be used by the *EmeraldUI* component to visually present the information of the managed schemes to the user.

¹⁷ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/catalogue-of-controls>

¹⁸ OSCAL: Open Security Controls Assessment Language, <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/>

3.6.1 Requirements

The requirements gathered for the RCM component are listed below:

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.01
Short title	Multi-schema support
Description	The repository should contain at least an additional security scheme, apart from the EUCS that is the scheme implemented in MEDINA Catalogue and is inherited in EMERALD.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	RCM, EmeraldUI
Source	DoA
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 4.1
Validation acceptance criteria	The user enters in the RCM, can see that several schemes are supported, and can navigate through them.
Progress	90%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.02
Short title	Accessible by the rest of components
Description	The repository content should be made accessible to the rest of EMERALD components via API.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	RCM, Clouditor-Orchestrator, EmeraldUI, MARI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	N.A.
Validation acceptance criteria	The API will be tested using an Open API client, and testing all available services.
Progress	90%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.03
Short title	Include metrics for all schemes supported
Description	The repository should include metrics that could be used to assess the compliance with one or more certification schemes.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must

Component	RCM, MARI, Clouditor-Orchestrator
Source	DoA, KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 4.1
Validation acceptance criteria	Check that RCM contains several metrics for each scheme defined in it. The checking can be done via user interface or via API.
Progress	30%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.04
Short title	Mapping of schemes
Description	The repository should support the mapping of the certification schemes contained. The scheme-to-scheme mapping will be provided by the MARI tool and stored in the repository. The rationale for the mapping decision will also be stored.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Should
Component	RCM, MARI
Source	DoA, KPI
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 3.1, KPI 3.3
Validation acceptance criteria	The user checks that security controls in a scheme are mapped to the controls in another scheme.
Progress	10%
Milestone	MS5: Components V2 (M24)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.05
Short title	Import/export of security schemes in OSCAL
Description	The repository is able to import a new scheme defined in the OSCAL language (this feature can also be used to update an existing scheme). The repository is able to export any available scheme in OSCAL format.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	RCM, EmeraldUI
Source	DoA
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 7.1, KPI 7.2

Validation acceptance criteria	Export: The user checks that the scheme is exported by creating a file in OSCAL format. Import: The user checks that the content of the repository is updated with the imported scheme.
Progress	25%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.06
Short title	Import/export of security schemes in CSV format
Description	The repository can export a scheme to a CSV file, and import a CSV file with the same format as a new scheme.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Could
Component	RCM, EmeraldUI
Source	Component
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 7.1
Validation acceptance criteria	Export: The user checks that the exported scheme is contained in a new file with CSV format.
Progress	60%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.07
Short title	Support for personalized catalogues
Description	The Repository has to offer the user the possibility to create a personalized catalogue of controls. These controls can be taken from the same or from different security schemes.
Status	Accepted
Priority	Must
Component	RCM, EmeraldUI
Source	Pilots
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 7.1, KPI 7.2
Validation acceptance criteria	The user should be able to define a new, particular catalogue, based on a set of selected controls.
Progress	0%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	RCM.08
Short title	Support updating/versioning of schemes

Description	The Repository has to maintain a versioning system of the schemes it contains, so that if a new version is uploaded, it is able to detect the change and notify the user that a new version is available
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Should
Component	RCM
Source	Pilots
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 7.1, KPI 7.2
Validation acceptance criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A new version of the certification scheme "X" is uploaded to the repository 2. A user using that scheme logs into the EMERALD system 3. The user receives a notification of the scheme version change
Progress	10%
Milestone	MS6: Integrated audit suite V2 (M30)

3.6.2 Design

The RCM can be decomposed in three main sub-components (see Figure 2), which are briefly described as follows:

- **Frontend:** This sub-component is the graphical user interface of the RCM. It allows users to filter the view and select the set of information they want to check from the existing schemes (e.g., controls of a certain scheme, requirements of a certain assurance level, metrics related to some controls, etc). At the time of writing, it has not yet been decided if this sub-component will be developed as part of the RCM or will be part of the *EmeraldUI* component. In any case, it will communicate with the backend via the API.
- **Backend:** This is the core sub-component of the RCM. It implements the APIs to perform the actual management of the scheme data, considering the filters set by the user through the UI or by calling the API. In a general microservices architecture, it can be composed of many general applications, each containing a few related entities and business rules. In our case, the RCM will contain two backends: i) *Backend converter*, which is dedicated to the scheme conversions to/from OSCAL, and ii) *Backend*, which deals with the management of schemes and metrics.
- **Registry:** This is an internal sub-component provided by the framework that is used to create a microservice architecture component that ties the other subcomponents together and enables them to communicate with each other.

In addition, data persistence is provided by a database connected to the backend.

Figure 2. Architecture of the Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM)

3.6.3 Integration

The RCM interacts with these other EMERALD components, as shown in Figure 1:

- **Clouditor-Orchestrator**, which retrieves the information about the schemes and the metrics from the RCM.
- **Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence (MARI)**, which provides the results of the mapping functionality to the RCM in order to store the results for further uses.
- **EmeraldUI**, which retrieves the information from the RCM to present it in the User Interface. On the other hand, the user may want to change the contents of the RCM by introducing new schemes, new versions of a scheme, or answering the self-assessment questionnaire.
- **AMOE**, a knowledge extractor that obtains from the RCM the definition of the security metrics needed to evaluate evidence from policy documents.

3.6.4 Planned Implementation

The RCM will be developed using Java and the JHipster Framework¹⁹. The framework provides all the needed mechanisms for a modern web application and a microservices architecture²⁰. JHipster uses Spring boot for application configuration.

On the client side, the *Frontend* gateway will use JavaScript, Yeoman, Webpack, Angular and Bootstrap technologies. On the server side, the *Backend* and the *Registry* will use Maven, Spring MVC REST for the API, Spring Data JPA, Netflix OSS²¹ and Python - Flask REST API²².

3.6.5 Advancements within EMERALD

The main development with respect to the *MEDINA Catalogue* will be the provision of an import/export mechanism for the schemes using standard languages, mainly OSCAL. In a first approach, we have already implemented such a mechanism for the EUCS scheme using CSV files.

Another added feature of the RCM with respect to the *MEDINA Catalogue* is the possibility to create ad-hoc schemes by the user. For this purpose, the OSCAL management mechanism will also be used.

3.7 Trustworthiness System (TWS)

The Trustworthiness System (TWS) for EMERALD is built up on the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* from the MEDINA project [8]. The TWS provides a secure mechanism for EMERALD to maintain an audit trail of evidence and assessment results. It is based on **Smart Contracts** backed by a **Blockchain network**, providing the following functionalities:

- Includes the logic for the *Clouditor-Assessment* to **provide the required information to be audited** (about evidence and assessment results).
- Provides **long-term secure information recording**, thanks to the inherent advantages of Blockchain (integrity, decentralization, authenticity...).

¹⁹ <https://www.jhipster.tech>

²⁰ <https://www.jhipster.tech/tech-stack/>

²¹ <https://www.jhipster.tech/microservices-architecture/>

²² <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/3.0.x/>

- Includes the logic for external users to **access and validate audited information** (about evidence and assessment results) in a **graphical and user-friendly way** through a frontend included in the EMERALD UI.

The TWS provides trustworthiness, fairness and transparency to the evidence and assessment results stored in EMERALD, as the integrity and authenticity of the information is guaranteed.

3.7.1 Requirements

The main requirements for the TWS component are:

Field	Description
Requirement ID	TWS.01
Short title	Provide integrity proof of evidence
Description	Provide a tool allowing the verification of evidence integrity without needing to store the evidence itself (for confidentiality reasons).
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	TWS & EmeraldUI
Source	DoA
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	N.A.
Validation acceptance criteria	This requirement should be validated by accessing the TWS component and checking the integrity of a piece of evidence when it has been modified and when it has not been modified.
Progress	50%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	TWS.02
Short title	Provide integrity proof of assessment results
Description	Provide a tool allowing the verification of assessment results integrity without needing to store the result itself (for confidentiality reasons).
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	TWS & EmeraldUI
Source	DoA
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	N.A.
Validation acceptance criteria	This requirement should be validated by accessing the TWS component and checking the integrity of an assessment result when it has been modified and when it has not been modified.
Progress	50%
Milestone	MS2: Components V1 (M12)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	TWS.03
Short title	Provide access through REST API or graphical interface
Description	The integrity validation of evidence and assessment results must be done through REST API or graphical interface (EMERALD UI).
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	TWS & EmeraldUI
Source	DoA
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	N.A.
Validation acceptance criteria	This requirement should be validated by making the integrity validation of evidence in both ways.
Progress	50%
Milestone	MS5: Components V2 (M24)

Field	Description
Requirement ID	TWS.04
Short title	Use a general-purpose public-private Blockchain network
Description	The TWS must be based on a real Blockchain network, with multiple nodes and multiple organizations to guarantee suitable decentralization and governance of the Blockchain network.
Status	Work in Progress
Priority	Must
Component	TWS
Source	DoA
Type	Technical
Related KR	KR7_INTEROP
Related KPI	KPI 7.2
Validation acceptance criteria	It will be validated with the final Blockchain network considered. The Blockchain network will not be locally deployed. An already existing network governed by externals will be considered to avoid security issues as information could not be modified in any way.
Progress	5%
Milestone	MS5: Components V2 (M24)

3.7.2 Design

Figure 3 shows the architecture of the Blockchain-based EMERALD TWS.

Figure 3. EMERALD Trustworthiness System (TWS) high-level architecture

The TWS is composed of five main elements:

- **Blockchain network.** A general-purpose Blockchain network will be considered for the prototyping of the TWS. At the time of writing, the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure has been considered.
- **Smart Contracts.** The TWS auditing functionalities have been implemented through Smart Contracts to be deployed on the Blockchain network (previous element). The Smart Contract functionalities include the registration of data in the Blockchain (evidence and assessment results) to be verified, as well as the use of this previously registered data for integrity verification. In addition, Blockchain-based events are also generated to feed the Blockchain viewer.
- **Blockchain Client.** Every *Assessment* component will have a Blockchain client to interact with the Blockchain and the Smart Contracts (wallet management, transactions generation, etc.).
- **Blockchain viewer.** It listens to Blockchain events from the Smart Contracts and normalises and categorises the details for proper visualization in a dashboard. The Blockchain viewer allows to isolate external users from the need to have a Blockchain client to consume information recorded on the Blockchain.
- **Automatic verification service:** An automatic verification tool for current and recorded evidence and assessment results is included in the TWS to provide auditors a user friendly and automatic way to verify the integrity of evidence and assessment results gathered in EMERALD. This service exposes a graphical interface to be integrated in the EMERALD UI.

3.7.3 Integration

The TWS interacts with two other components of the EMERALD solution (see Figure 1):

- **Clouditor-Assessment:** The interaction with this component will take place in two different ways:
 1. The *Assessment* component provides the information related to evidence and assessment results to be recorded in the Blockchain.
 2. The automatic verification service requests the current values of evidence and assessment results stored in the EMERALD's internal evidence storage for fair

integrity validation against the information previously recorded in the Blockchain.

- **EmeraldUI:** The graphical interface of the TWS automatic verification service is integrated into the EMERALD UI so that auditors can easily verify the trustworthiness of evidence and assessment results, and determine whether they can trust on them.

3.7.4 Planned Implementation

The most important update for the TWS is its deployment in a real general-purpose public-private Blockchain network. Initially, the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI) has been considered. EBSI is a network of distributed blockchain nodes across different countries in Europe. It is the first EU-wide blockchain infrastructure, driven by the public sector and in full respect of European values and regulations, which aims to provide cross-border services for public administrations, businesses, citizens and their ecosystems to verify information and make services trustworthy. EBSI already provides services related to citizens identity in Europe through the Blockchain based Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) technology. From EMERALD, our aim is to extend EBSI with a new European trustworthiness system for guaranteeing evidence integrity in auditing processes. In this sense, a proposal for piloting the TWS in EBSI has already been submitted to EBSI by TECNALIA with collaboration of NIXU and all the EMERALD pilots, and it is currently under consideration.

Beyond that, the functionality and performance of TWS will be improved based on the feedback of the pilot validation.

3.7.5 Advancements within EMERALD

The TWS main functionalities were already developed in the MEDINA project: evidence and assessment results storage in the Blockchain, graphical visualization by external users and automatic verification against the current values available in the assessment component. However, the TWS was just a prototype in MEDINA that needs to be enhanced in EMERALD in three main aspects:

- Deploying the TWS functionality on a real general purpose Blockchain network to allow fair and transparent functionality (in MEDINA, it was deployed in a dummy Blockchain network for validation purposes).
- Analysing the existing implementation for improvements or updates to improve system performance, as the use of Blockchain often degrades performance.
- Enabling automatic verification of evidence or assessment results in EMERALD (in MEDINA, verification was always performed on demand).

4 Conclusions

This document provides an overview of the overall architecture and key objectives of the WP3 components in the EMERALD framework. Subsequently, we have detailed all the EMERALD components within WP3, including the *Clouditor-Orchestrator*, *Clouditor-Assessment*, *Clouditor-Evidence Store*, *Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence (MARI)*, *Clouditor-Evaluation*, *Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM)*, and *Trustworthiness System (TWS)*. The requirements, design, integration, planned implementation, and advancements of each component within the EMERALD project have been thoroughly described.

This deliverable sets the foundation for the subsequent development and integration phases of the project. It outlines the current state of each component and the planned enhancements, providing a clear roadmap for achieving the project's objectives.

Future steps involve the implementation and integration as outlined in deliverables D3.3 and D3.5. Specifically, D3.3 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Implementation-v1” (M12) will focus on the implementation details of the WP3 components, while D3.5 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Integration-v1” (M15) will address the interim integration of these components into the overall EMERALD system.

5 References

- [1] EMERALD Consortium, “EMERALD - Annex 1 - Description of Action - GA 101120688,” 2022.
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- [3] EMERALD Consortium, “D1.1 Data Modelling and Interaction Mechanisms,” 2024.
- [4] EMERALD Consortium, “D2.1 Graph Ontology for Evidence Storage,” 2024.
- [5] EMERALD Consortium, “D4.1 Results of the UI-UX requirements analysis and the work processes–v1,” 2024.
- [6] EMERALD Consortium, “D5.1 Pilot definition, set-up & validation plan,” 2024.
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- [8] MEDINA Consortium, “D5.5 MEDINA integrated solution-v3 (<https://medina-project.eu/public-deliverables/>),” 2023.
- [9] EMERALD Consortium, “D2.1 Graph Ontology for Evidence Storage,” 2024.